

Unreliable Automatic Language Translation

On the basis of selected examples, it will be examined whether language translation programs (DeepL translator and Google translate) are reliable and whether they are capable of learning. Do the programs understand what they generate?

By Herbert Bruderer

Part 1

Has there been any progress with technical terms?

First translation: 2023

Second translation: 2025

Errors are marked in red.

Source text

Manche wissenschaftliche Bücher haben sowohl ein Geleitwort wie auch ein Vorwort.

Google translate

Some scholarly books have both **a foreword and a foreword**.

Some scientific books have both a foreword and a preface.

DeepL

Some scientific books have both **a preface and a preface**.

Some academic books have both a foreword and a preface.

Source text

Kennen Sie den Unterschied zwischen einem Geleit- und einem Vorwort?

Google translate

Do you know the difference between **an introduction and a foreword**?

Do you know the difference between a foreword and a preface?

DeepL

Do you know the difference between **a preface and a foreword**?

Do you know the difference between a foreword and a preface?

Source text

Das Geleitwort stammt beispielsweise vom Herausgeber, das Vorwort von der Verfasserin.

Google translate

For example, the **foreword** comes from the editor, the **foreword** from the author.

For example, the foreword comes from the editor, the preface from the author.

DeepL

For example, the **foreword** comes from the editor, the **foreword** from the author.

The foreword, for example, is written by the editor, the preface by the author.

Geleitwort means foreword, Vorwort equals preface.

Source text

Wir unterscheiden mehrere Arten von Rechenschiebern: Rechenstäbe, Rechenscheiben, Rechenwalzen und Rechenuhren.

Google translate

We differentiate between several types of slide rules: **slide rules, slide discs, slide rulers and slide clocks.**

We distinguish between several types of slide rules: **slide rods, slide discs, slide rollers and slide clocks.**

DeepL

We distinguish between several types of slide rules: **rake rods, calculating discs, rake rollers and slide clocks.**

There are several types of slide rules: **slide rules, slide discs, slide rollers and slide clocks.**

Source text

Rechenschieber wie Rechenstäbe, Rechenscheiben, Rechentrommeln und Rechenuhren sind analoge Rechenhilfsmittel.

Google translate

Slide rules such as **slide rules, slide discs, slide drums and calculator clocks** are analogue computing aids.

Slide rules such as **slide rods, slide discs, slide drums and slide clocks** are analogue calculating aids.

DeepL

Slide rules such as **rake rods, calculating discs, calculating drums and calculating clocks** are analogue calculating aids.

Slide rules such as **slide rules, calculating discs, calculating drums and calculating clocks** are analog calculating aids.

First translation: 2019

Second translation: 2020

Third translation: 2023

Fourth translation: 2025

Errors are marked in red.

Source text

Es gibt hauptsächlich drei Arten analoger Rechenschieber: Rechenstäbe, Rechenscheiben und Rechenwalzen.

Google translate

2019: There are mainly three types of analogue slide rules: **rulers, calculating discs and raking rollers.**

2020: There are three main types of analog slide rules: **slide rules, calculating discs and calculating rollers.**

2023: There are three main types of analog slide rules: **slide rules, slide discs and slide rulers.**

2025: There are mainly three types of analog slide rules: **slide rods, slide discs and slide rollers.**

DeepL

2019: There are mainly three types of analog slide rules: **slide bars, slide disks and rake rollers.**

2020: There are three main types of analog slide rules: **slide rules, discs and rollers.**

2023: There are mainly three types of analog slide rules: **rake rods, discs and rake rollers.**

2025: There are three main types of analog slide rules: **slide rules, slide discs and slide rollers.**

Source text

Zu den wichtigsten Formen der Rechenschieber gehören der Rechenstab, die Rechenscheibe, die Rechenwalze und die Rechenuhr.

Google translate

2019: Among the most important forms of slide rule are **the ruler, the ruler, the rake and the ruler.**

2020: The most important forms of slide rule include **the slide rule, the calculation disk, the calculation roller and the calculation clock.**

2023: The most important forms of slide rule include **the slide rule, the slide disc, the slide rule and the slide clock.**

2025: The most important forms of slide rules include **the slide rule, the slide disc, the slide cylinder and the slide clock.**

DeepL

2019: The most important forms of slide rules are **the slide bar, the disc rule, the screen roller and the screen clock.**

2020: The most important forms of slide rules are the **slide rule, the disc rule, the roller rule and the clock.**

2023: The most important forms of slide rule include **the rake stick, the calculating disc, the calculating roller and the calculating clock.**

2025: The most important types of slide rule include **the slide rule, the slide rule disk, the slide rule roller and the slide rule clock.**

Correct technical terms

Rechenscheibe = circular slide rule

Rechenschieber = slide rule

Rechenstab = linear slide rule

Rechentrommel = cylindrical slide rule

Rechenuhr = pocket watch slide rule

Rechenwalze = cylindrical slide rule

Source text

Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz gilt als Erfinder des Sprossenrads und der Staffelwalze.

Google translate

2019: Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz is regarded as the inventor of **the sprocket wheel and the squadron roller.**

2020: Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz is considered the inventor of **the sprout wheel and the graduated roller.**

2023: Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz is regarded as the inventor of **the sprocket wheel and the stepped roller.**

2025: Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz is considered the inventor of **the pinion wheel and the stepped roller.**

DeepL

2019: Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz is regarded as the inventor of **the sprocket wheel and the relay roller**.

2020: Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz is considered the inventor of **the sprocket wheel and the relay roller**.

2023: Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz is considered the inventor of **the rung wheel and the relay roller**.

2025: Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz is considered the inventor of **the rung wheel and the graduated roller**.

Correct technical terms

Sprossenrad = pinwheel

Staffelwalze = stepped drum

Conclusion

In most cases, the learning ability in automatic language translation seems to be rather limited. Some translations are unreliable, while others are unusable.

Part 2

I have tried to translate two simple sentences from German into English, French, Italian and Spanish. The program has to distinguish between the 2nd person singular, the 2nd person plural and the courtesy form. English does not distinguish between these forms, so the translations are easy. The programs often do not recognize the differences, especially when translating into Italian and Spanish.

First translation: 2023

Second translation: 2025

Errors are marked in red.

Weißt du, wann das Haus gebaut wurde?

Google translate

Do you know when the house was built?

Savez-vous quand la maison a été construite?

Savez-vous quand la maison a été construite ?

Sai quando è stata costruita la casa?

Sai quando è stata costruita la casa?

¿Sabes cuándo se construyó la casa?

¿Sabes cuándo se construyó la casa?

DeepL

Do you know when the house was built?

Savez-vous quand la maison a été construite ?

Tu sais quand cette maison a été construite ?

Sai quando è stata costruita la casa?
Sa quando è stata costruita la casa?

¿Sabes cuándo se construyó la casa?
¿Sabe cuándo se construyó la casa?

Wisst ihr, wann das Haus gebaut wurde?

Google translate

Do you know when the house was built?

Savez-vous quand la maison a été construite?
Savez-vous quand cette maison a été construite ?

Sai quando è stata costruita la casa?
Sai quando è stata costruita la casa?

¿Sabes cuándo se construyó la casa?
¿Sabes cuándo se construyó la casa?

DeepL

Do you know when the house was built?

Savez-vous quand la maison a été construite ?
Savez-vous quand cette maison a été construite ?

Sai quando è stata costruita la casa?
Sa quando è stata costruita la casa?

¿Sabes cuándo se construyó la casa?
¿Sabe cuándo se construyó la casa?

Wissen Sie, wann das Haus gebaut wurde?

Google translate

Do you know when the house was built?

Savez-vous quand la maison a été construite?
Savez-vous quand la maison a été construite ?

Sai quando è stata costruita la casa?
Sai quando è stata costruita la casa?

¿Sabes cuándo se construyó la casa?
¿Sabes cuándo se construyó la casa?

DeepL

Do you know when the house was built?

Savez-vous quand la maison a été construite ?
Savez-vous quand la maison a été construite ?

Sai quando è stata costruita la casa?
Sa quando è stata costruita la casa?

¿Sabes cuándo se construyó la casa?
¿Sabe cuándo se construyó la casa?

Bitte gib dieses Paket deiner Schwester, wenn sie nach Hause kommt.

Google translate

Please give this package to your sister when she comes home.

S'il vous plaît donner ce paquet à votre soeur quand elle rentre à la maison.
S'il vous plaît, donnez ce paquet à votre sœur quand elle rentrera à la maison.

Per favore consegna questo pacchetto a tua sorella quando torna a casa.
Per favore, consegna questo pacco a tua sorella quando torna a casa.

Por favor, dale este paquete a tu hermana cuando regrese a casa.
Por favor, dale este paquete a tu hermana cuando llegue a casa.

DeepL

Please give this package to your sister when she gets home.

S'il vous plaît, donnez ce paquet à votre soeur quand elle rentrera à la maison.
S'il te plaît, donne ce paquet à ta sœur quand elle rentrera à la maison.

Per favore, dai questo pacco a tua sorella quando torna a casa.
La prego di dare questo pacco a sua sorella quando torna a casa.

Por favor, dale este paquete a tu hermana cuando llegue a casa.
Por favor, dale este paquete a tu hermana cuando llegue a casa.

Conclusions

The progress in automatic language translation is sobering.

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